

Evidence-Based Practice in Nursing

A brief guide

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Notes on Evidence-Based Practice (EBP)

What it IS

- Evidence-based practice IS using the **best available evidence** from the scientific literature
- Evidence-based practice IS using **your own clinical judgement**
- Evidence-based practice IS including your **patient's/family's values and preferences**

What it IS NOT

- Evidence-based practice does NOT include **qualitative studies**
- Evidence-based practice does NOT mean **doing your own research** (although you certainly can if you want to!)
- Evidence-based practice is NOT **simply following traditions, authority or habits** (sacred cows)

EBP in Nursing—2 Definitions

Definition 1

"Evidence based nursing practice is the conscientious, explicit and judicious use of theory-derived, research-based information in making decisions about care delivery to individuals or groups of patients and in consideration of individual needs and preferences"

[Ingersoll, G. L. (2000). Evidence-based nursing: What it is and what it isn't. *Nursing Outlook*, 48(4), 151-152.]

Definition 2

"Evidence-based practice is a paradigm and life-long problem solving approach to clinical decision-making that involves the conscientious use of the *best available evidence with one's own clinical expertise and patient values and preferences* to improve outcomes for individuals, groups, communities and systems"

[Melnyk, B & Fineout-Overholt, E. (2011). Evidence-based practice in nursing and healthcare. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, p. 595.]

Note: The published evidence, by itself, does not make the decision, but it can help support the patient care process.

The full integration of these three components –

1) *the best available evidence*

2) *one's own clinical expertise*

3) *patient & family values and preferences*

into clinical decisions enhances the opportunity for optimal clinical outcomes and quality of life.

EBP Case Example

The practice of EBP is usually triggered by patient encounters which generate questions about the effects of therapy, the utility of diagnostic tests, the prognosis of diseases, and/or the etiology of disorders.

Evidence-Based Practice requires new skills of the clinician, including efficient literature searching, and the application of formal rules of evidence in evaluating the clinical literature.

Ask a Good Clinical Question Using PICO

Sometimes a situation comes up that calls into question a traditional practice (or *Sacred Cow*). It's necessary to look at the published literature to see if there is evidence for this practice. To do this it helps to frame your question according to the PICO framework.

Mooo . . .
We've ALWAYS
used **cold** for
24 hours, **then**
heat!

What is PICO?

PICO is a mnemonic that helps you remember the key components of a well-focused question. The question needs to identify the **key problem** of the patient, what **treatment or tests** you are considering for the patient, what **alternative treatment or tests** are being considered (if any) and what is the **desired outcome**.

- P Patient Problem**
- I Intervention**
- C Comparison**
- O Outcome**

In the case of our EBP case example, the question would be framed like this:

- P Muscle pain from a sports injury in 35 yr. old male**
- I Apply heat from the time of onset**
- C Apply cold for 24 hours first, then switch to heat**
- O Pain reduction**

Written out as a search question it would look like this:

In otherwise healthy adults with pain from muscle injuries, how effective is it to use just heat on sore muscles compared with using cold for 24 hours and then switching to heat?

Types of PICO Questions

The question of heat or cold for muscle pain is a **Therapy** question. There can be other types of EBP questions too:

- **THERAPY** – around a disease or condition
- **PREVENTION** – emphasis on patient actions prior to condition
- **DIAGNOSIS** – identifying a disease or condition
- **PROGNOSIS** – severity and duration of clinical problem
- **ETIOLOGY** – emphasis on environmental triggers or source of condition

A more detailed view:

Question Type	Patient, Problem	Intervention or Exposure	Comparison	Outcome Measures
Treatment (Therapy)	The patient's disease or condition.	A therapeutic measure, ex., a medication, surgical intervention, or life style change.	Standard of care, another intervention, or a placebo.	Ex: mortality rate, days lost from work, pain, disability.
Prevention	The patient's risk factors and general health condition.	A preventive measure, e.g., a medication or a life style change.	May not be applicable.	Ex: disease incidence, mortality rate, days lost from work.
Diagnosis	The target disease or condition.	A diagnostic test or procedure.	The current "reference standard" or "gold standard" test for the problem.	Measures of the test utility, ex., sensitivity, specificity, odds ratio.
Prognosis (Natural History)	The main prognostic factor or clinical problem in terms of its severity and duration.	The exposure of interest is usually time , sometimes expressed as "watchful waiting".	Usually not applicable. Identify the standard treatment if your question is about "watchful waiting".	Ex: survival rates, mortality rates, rates disease progression.
Etiology or Harm (Causation)	Your patient's risk factors, current health disorders or general health condition	The intervention or exposure of interest, including some indication of the strength (dose) of the risk factor and the duration of the exposure.	May not be applicable.	Ex: disease incidence, rates of disease progression, mortality rates.

From: Melnyk, B. M., & Fineout-Overholt, E. (2011). Evidence-based practice in nursing & healthcare: A guide to best practice. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

PICO Questions

Nursing vs. Medicine

It is important that your PICO question reflects nursing practice, *particularly if you are using this as a basis for research.*

Nursing: In otherwise healthy adults with pain from muscle injuries, how effective is it to use just heat on sore muscles compared with using cold for 24 hours and then switching to heat?

Medicine: In otherwise healthy adults with pain from muscle injuries, what is the effect of oxycodone as compared with NSAIDs?

PICO(T)

Sometimes a (T) is added where T = Time

Examples of other types of PICO Questions

Here is an example of a PREVENTION question.

For _____ does the use of _____ reduce the future risk of _____ compared with _____?

For **sun exposure**, does the use of **sunscreen with SPF 50** reduce the future risk of **skin cancer** compared with **SPF 30**?

Here is an example of a DIAGNOSIS question.

Are (Is) _____ equally/more effective in diagnosing _____ compared with _____?

Is **the Richmond Agitation-Sedation Scale (RASS)** more effective in diagnosing **patients' aggressive tendencies** compared with **nursing subjective clinical assessment**?

Examples of other types of PICO questions

Here is an example of a **PROGNOSIS** question.

Does _____ influence _____ in patients who have _____?

Does **mindful meditation** influence **quality of life** in patients who have **cancer**?

Here is an example of an **ETIOLOGY** question.

Are _____ who are _____ at greater risk for/of _____ compared with _____ who are not _____?

Are **children** who are **sleep deprived** at greater risk of **obesity** compared with **children** who are not **sleep deprived**?

Types of Studies

In otherwise healthy adults with pain from muscle injuries, how effective is it to use just heat on sore muscles compared with using cold for 24 hours and then switching to heat?

Our heroine has framed her question according to the PICO framework and is now ready to think about the types of studies she should look for in the literature to help her answer her question.

For starters, she should look for a quantitative study.

COMPARISON OF QUANTITATIVE & QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

PARAMETERS	QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH	QUALITATIVE RESEARCH
GENERAL NATURE	Objective approach to seek precise measurement in numerical form	Subjective approach to seek in-depth description in narrative form
KNOWLEDGE OF STUDY VARIABLE	Variables are clearly understood & defined in advance by the researcher	Researcher may have only rough idea about variables in advance.

Slide from: <http://www.slideshare.net/maheswarijaikumar/quantitative-vs-qualitative-research>

It's best to use QUANTITATIVE research to support evidence-based practice.

Qualitative research is not considered to be strong evidence in the evidence hierarchy.

Not all questions lend themselves to the same types of study. Let's look at a flowchart to help outline some major study types . . .

Study-type flow chart:

From Grimes and Schulz, *Lancet*, 359:57-61, 2002

Levels of Evidence

The quality of evidence from a study varies with the type of study.

Better evidence is found toward the top of the pyramid.

Case-Control Studies

Image from: <http://library.downstate.edu/EBM2/2500.htm>

Case control studies are studies in which patients who already have a certain condition are compared with people who do not.

Advantages of Case-Control Studies:

- **They can be done quickly.** By asking patients about their past history, researchers can quickly discover effects that otherwise would take many years to show themselves.
- Researchers **don't need special methods**, control groups, etc. They just take the people who show up at their institution with a particular condition and ask them a few questions.
- The **first study to suggest a new medical conclusion will often be a case control study**, perhaps designed to check on a hypothesis suggested by a *case series*. If possible, researchers will generally try to confirm the results with a randomized controlled trial or a cohort study

Disadvantage:

- Case control studies are less reliable than either *randomized controlled trials* or *cohort studies*. **Just because there is a statistical relationship between two conditions does not mean that one condition actually caused the other.** For instance, lung cancer rates are higher for people without a college education (who tend to smoke more), but that does not mean that someone can reduce his or her cancer risk just by getting a college education.

From: <http://library.downstate.edu/EBM2/2500.htm>

A Real-life Example of a Case-Control Study:

How a Medical Mystery in Brazil Led Doctors to Zika

“Zika’s connection to microcephaly was suspected but very difficult to confirm. Dr. Turchi set up a quick “*case control*” study, the epidemiologist’s classic tool, comparing babies born with the condition and those without it.”

[From: McNeil, Donald G. Jr., Romero, Simon & Tavernise, Sabrina (2016, February 6). How a Medical Mystery in Brazil Led Doctors to Zika. *The New York Times*, Health. <http://nyti.ms/23Q6bYu>]

Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus*, one of the species that can carry the Zika virus, begins its blood meal. (Photo: James Gathany, CDC)

Cohort Studies

Image from: <http://library.downstate.edu/EBM2/2400.htm>

A Cohort Study is a study in which patients who presently have a certain condition and/or receive a particular treatment are followed over time and compared with another group who are not affected by the condition under investigation.

Advantages of Cohort Studies:

- Can reveal the length of **time between exposure and outcome**.
- Can look at **several outcomes**.
- Can be done where there is **accidental or voluntary exposure**, (where it would be unethical to assign exposure as is done in a randomized controlled trial)
- Somewhat **less potential for bias** than case-control studies.

Disadvantages:

- **Not as reliable as randomized controlled trials:** The two groups may differ in ways other than in the variable under study. For example, if the subjects who smoke tend to have less money than the non-smokers, and thus have less access to health care, that would exaggerate the difference between the two groups.
- **They can end up taking a very long time:** Things tend to change over the course of the study. People die, move away, or develop other conditions, new and promising treatments arise, and so on.

From: <http://library.downstate.edu/EBM2/2400.htm>

Cohort Study

A Real-Life Example:

The effect of working for pay on adolescent tobacco use

This study uses data collected from high school students from Baltimore, Maryland, and studies the differences in initiation of tobacco use between:

- a cohort of adolescents that started working for pay
- a cohort of adolescents that did not work.

The results suggest that adolescents who work for pay have a higher risk of initiating tobacco use.

[Ramchand, R., Jalongo, N. S., & Chilcoat, H. D. (2007). The effect of working for pay on adolescent tobacco use. *American Journal of Public Health*, 97(11), 2056-2062.]

<http://himmelfarb.gwu.edu/tutorials/studydesign101/cohorts.html>

Observational Studies at a Glance

Case Control Studies and Cohort Studies are both **OBSERVATIONAL** designs. In an observational study investigators observe subjects and measure variables of interest without assigning treatments to the subjects. The treatment that each subject receives is determined beyond the control of the investigator.

Observational studies are often used rather than intervention or experimental studies when:

- Ethically treatments (like smoking) or conditions (like a disease state) cannot be introduced
- When research in an area is just starting and introduction or manipulation of conditions is not yet warranted

Randomized Controlled Trials

In the case of our nurse heroine, the PICO question she is asking would best be answered by a randomized controlled trial.

This **EXPERIMENTAL** study type is considered to be strong evidence in the world of evidence-based practice.

A randomized controlled trial randomly divides study subjects into two or more groups: an intervention group or groups, and a control group.

Intervention group = adult male patients with muscle pain who are given only heat to treat.

Control group = adult male patients with muscle pain who are given cold packs for 24 hours and then switched to heat.

It is important that study subjects are **assigned RANDOMLY** to the groups. This helps **prevent BIAS** in the study.

Randomized Controlled Trials

Advantages:

- Assigning patients at random **reduces the risk of bias** and increases the probability that differences between the groups can be attributed to the treatment.

Disadvantages:

- With **certain research questions**, randomized controlled studies **cannot be done for ethical reasons**.

Randomized controlled trials are the standard method of answering questions about the effectiveness of different therapies.

Our nurse heroine doesn't have to DO this study (although this is certainly possible). She should start by looking in the published literature to see if others have already done such a study. She can then use her findings as evidence to support her patient care decisions.

Remember EBP is . . .

A Real-world Example of a Randomized Controlled Trial

Continuous low-level heat wrap therapy for the prevention and early phase treatment of delayed-onset muscle soreness of the low back: a randomized controlled trial.

This article reports on the effect of heat vs. cold therapy for treating delayed onset muscle soreness (DOMS).

- A control group of participants was given standard cold pack therapy after performing vigorous exercise to induce low back DOMS
- The experimental group of participants was given heat-wrap therapy

At 24 hours post-exercise, the study found a significant reduction in pain with the heat-wrap therapy as compared with cold therapy.

[Mayer, J., Mooney, V., Matheson, L., Erasala, G., Verna, J., Udermann, B., & Leggett, S. (2006). Continuous low-level heat wrap therapy for the prevention and early phase treatment of delayed-onset muscle soreness of the low back: a randomized controlled trial. *Archives Of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation*, 87(10), 1310-1317.]

Other Study Designs

There are a couple of other types of study designs that you should be aware of:

Pre-experimental Designs

- Subjects are observed after an intervention or treatment
- There is no pretest, and/or no control or comparison group
- There is no randomization

Quasi-experimental Designs

- Similar to randomized controlled trials but . . .
- Lack randomized assignment

Library Resources

You have a professional question—where do you look?

The best type of study to answer the therapy question of heat or cold for back pain would be a randomized controlled trial.
How do I find one??

You could . . .

- Ask a colleague
- Google it
- Look in a textbook
- Use a library database OR

Ask a librarian!

Many people hesitate to use library resources or ask a librarian . . .

What – you don't know the secret code??

But the UCH library has great resources and friendly, helpful librarians.

How can I help you?

Call (860) 670-3808, or e-mail ref@uchc.edu to learn more about how the library can help you.

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